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Revision of the Qualification Framework at the Technical University of Denmark

Part 2: Applications

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ABSTRACT

Using a revised Qualification Framework (QF) with four main categories: *-to know*, *- to be*, *-to interact*, and *-to do*, this paper demonstrates how to use the elements of the QF to construct Programme-Qualification Matrices. A general Programme-Qualification Matrix defines the qualifications and their respective conceptual understanding common to all engineering programmes. This is complemented by programme-specific qualification matrices with added emphasis on content and context. Redesigned educational outcomes for three bachelor programmes are presented to demonstrate the versatility of the concept.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum development, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Programme-qualification matrix, educational outcomes, constructive alignment

INTRODUCTION

In a companion paper [1], revisions to the Danish National Qualification Framework (NQF) were proposed in order to facilitate more detailed design and evaluation of engineering programmes at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). The organization of the proposed qualification framework is repeated here for the reader's convenience.

Table 1. Components of a revised qualification framework [1]

1 st level	2 nd level descriptors	Description
1: - To know	Knowledge of theories	Acquire and apply terminology and facts, theories, laws of nature, methods, and procedures.
	Knowledge of praxis	Apply knowledge about praxis-induced boundary conditions and their influence on the applicability of theories and methods.
2: - To be	Mind-set	Develop a personal and professional mind-set.
	Self-instruction	Identify need for new knowledge, gather resources, execute, and evaluate learning outcomes.
3: - To interact	Teamwork	Conduct, coordinate, lead, monitor, and develop teamwork.
	Communication	Master language and tools, structure content, choose between narrative styles, edit for logic and clarity, and define communication objectives and receiver competencies.
4: - To do	Operative skills	Advance degree of training, from novice to expert, in executing manual and cognitive tasks.
	Problem solving	Interpret problem information, identify objective, diagnose problem, choose strategy, execute and evaluate solution, interpret impact of solution.

In this paper, the revised framework is used to define educational outcomes for three programmes in B.Sc. in Engineering.

1 PROGRAMME QUALIFICATION MATRICES

1.1 Common qualification elements

The proposed Qualification Framework for programmes at the Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) level can be divided into elements common to all programmes and elements that are specific to the individual programmes. In this section, the common elements are presented in a *Programme-Qualification Matrix* with Programme-Outcomes listed along the vertical axis and Course levels listed along the horizontal axis.

Table 2 describes the elements of the qualification framework, which are common to all engineering programmes. Levels of *process and element complexity* are indicated by italicised keywords defined in a companion paper [1]. In the four columns to the right, course numbers are to be entered, ordered from left to right by a ranking of object/subject complexity [1]. Multiple course numbers can be entered into each cell. Here fictive course numbers have been used. *Generic foundation* courses (Gen.) are 100-level (courses with no prerequisites), *Discipline core* courses (Cor.) are 200-level (first-level engineering courses) and *Discipline specialization* courses (Spe.) are 300-level (second-level engineering courses). *Capstone* courses (Cap.) relate here to

project courses, hands-on courses, internships, and thesis work. Learning activities in the *Capstone* category are annotated in the rightmost column using the following abbreviations: First semester project (1SP), fourth semester project (4SP), hands-on course (HO), B. Sc. Project (BSc).

Table 2. Programme-Qualification Matrix. Common elements. Fictive course numbers

		Object complexity→			
		Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
	-To know				
XXX.K1	Knowledge of natural science: Can <i>classify, explain, and interpret</i> facts, terminology, principles, generalisations, theories, models, methods, and procedures within mathematics, physics, chemistry, statistics, and biology, and can <i>apply</i> this knowledge to <i>analyse, evaluate, and solve</i> technical problems.	101 102 103 104 105	201 202 203		1SP 4SP
XXX.K2	Knowledge of information technology: Can <i>use</i> a programming language and independently <i>design, implement, test, and document</i> software for technical problem solving. Can, in addition, <i>explain theories and algorithms underlying</i> general and specialised software for data acquisition, visualisation, analysis, design, and simulation.	106			1SP 4SP
XXX.K3	Knowledge of science: Can <i>understand and assess</i> the relationship between scientific knowledge and practical experience in creating new technologies, types of knowledge and competences, building the foundation of engineering and the work involved in technological solutions, and the qualities of technologies, and its historic dependency and importance in the development of society.			307	4SP BSc
	-To be				
XXX.B1	Personal and professional mind-set: Embodies <i>self-efficacy, positive social attitude, and self-governance</i> . Is <i>process-oriented</i> with a hypothesis- and need-driven curiosity, and evidence-based creativity. Thinks logically and critically. Actualize <i>product-oriented</i> entrepreneurship founded on safety, reliability, sustainability, usability, serviceability, aesthetics, and ethics.	111 121	211 221 241	321	1SP 4SP BSc
XXX.B2	Self-instruction: Is <i>self-reflective, need-aware, and metacognitive</i> . Can orchestrate resources, execute and evaluate learning. Is familiar with and can sort critically between sources of information within the discipline.	121	221 251	321	4SP BSc
	-To interact				
XXX.I1	Communication: Master oral and written <i>language and communication tools</i> expertly, <i>structure content</i> to norms, perform <i>editorial editing</i> , can use a variety of <i>narrative styles</i> in accord with the standards of the context. Can, through <i>context analysis</i> , define the objective of the communication and take into account the competencies of the receiver.	111 121	211 241	321	1SP 4SP BSc
XXX.I2	Team work: Can <i>execute tasks</i> in teams while observing codes of behaviour, effort, ethics and accountability. Can take responsibility for <i>coordination, leadership, process monitoring, and team and individual development</i> .	121	221 251	321	1SP 4SP BSc

	...continued	Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
	-To do				
XXX.D1	Skills – general: Can execute complex cognitive and manual procedures effectively and with <i>precision</i> and use advanced tools correctly and independently. Can <i>see the goal of the task, adapt procedures</i> and <i>visualize solutions</i> .	111 121	211 221 231 241 251	311 321 341	1SP 4SP BSc
XXX.D2	Problem solving - general: Can solve complex closed and open problems in <i>procedural</i> steps with complex, incomplete and imprecise problem descriptions. Can <i>reduce</i> a complex problem to an idealized problem and evaluate the consequences thereof. Can <i>diagnose</i> a problem, <i>identify</i> the objective, <i>sort</i> between valid and invalid solution methods, and argue a <i>strategy</i> for choosing between valid methods. Can <i>judge</i> the validity, strengths, and weaknesses of solutions. Can <i>interpret</i> the impact of the solution to the problem sphere.	111 121	211 221 231 241 251	311 321 341	1SP 4SP BSc

1.2 Programme specific elements – Biomedical Engineering

The common elements of the Programme-Qualification Matrix must be complemented by a set of programme-specific qualification elements. In *Table 3*, programme-specific qualifications are listed for the B. Sc. programme in Biomedical Engineering. This programme started in 2003, enrolls 60 students annually, and offers courses in biosignals, biomedical imaging, biosystems, bioinstrumentation, biomechanics, biomaterials, biotransport, and cellular signalling. As for the common elements in *Table 2*, the depth of learning is indicated by italicized descriptors. In the common qualifications (*Table 2*), focus is on defining the level of conceptual understanding. In the programme-specific qualifications (*Table 3*), the descriptions complement with content and context. Course numbers are real, but with department prefix removed. Course level is not indicated by the first digit, only by its placement in the four rightmost columns.

Table 3. Programme-Qualification Matrix. Biomedical Engineering

		Object complexity→			
	-To know	Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
BME.K1	Knowledge of health science: Can <i>classify</i> cellular structures, anatomy and physiology of organ systems, and <i>explain</i> form and function with correct use of terminology. Can <i>analyse</i> and <i>interpret</i> histochemical preparations, <i>apply</i> biophysical principles, and <i>analyse</i> and <i>interpret</i> results of experiments. Can <i>define</i> diseases and <i>explain</i> pathogenesis and aetiology. Can <i>account</i> for symptoms and methods for diagnosis and treatment.	K02	K03 K11		1SP 4SP BSc
BME.K2	Knowledge of health-care praxis: Can <i>describe</i> and <i>explain</i> the rationale for technology applied in diagnosis and treatment. Can <i>explain</i> and <i>analyse</i> how technical factors influence the quality of clinical examinations. Can <i>describe</i> methods for evaluating accuracy and reproducibility of clinical procedures.			K04 K06	HO BSc

	...continued	Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
BME.K3	Knowledge of biomedical engineering: Can <i>classify, explain, and interpret</i> facts, terminology, principles, theories, models, methods, and procedures within electrical circuits, biomedical instrumentation, signal processing, biomedical imaging, material science, biomechanics, biofluids, biotransport, and biosystems modelling. Can <i>apply</i> this knowledge to <i>analyse</i> and <i>solve</i> biomedical engineering problems.	501 502	K10 512 520 540 605 650	K05 511 522	1SP 4SP BSc
BME.K4	Knowledge of biomedical engineering praxis: Can <i>list</i> the major biomedical engineering companies, <i>describe</i> their product lines and <i>list</i> the main qualifications required in these companies. Can for specific disciplines <i>account</i> for praxis and regulatory induced limitations to the applications of theories, methods, and materials.	502	512 520 540 650		BSc
	-To do				
BME.D1	Clinical skills: Can <i>apply</i> general codes of hygiene and conduct in health-care environments. Can <i>assist</i> clinical staff in measurements, data analysis, and trouble shooting. Can <i>instruct</i> clinical staff about correct use of biomedical equipment, and their strengths and limitations.			K04 K06	4SP BSc
BME.D2	Technical skills: Can <i>setup</i> and <i>operate</i> systems for test and measurement and acquire data in a reproducible manner. Can <i>design</i> and <i>implement</i> software for analysis and visualisation of data. Can <i>perform</i> systems check and calibration, and make corrections and simple repair to medical equipment.	501 502	K10 540	598	HO BSc
BME.D3	Problem solving – Investigative: Can assist in hypothesis-driven research within cell biology and organ physiology, within signal and image processing with implementation of problem specific software, within biomechanics, biofluid mechanics and biotransport with model development, mathematical analysis, computer simulations, experiments, and data analysis.	501 502	K10 520 605	K05 522 561	4SP HO BSc
BME.D4	Problem solving – Creative: Can assist in need-driven development of programmable products by design and construction of analog electronics and with software development for systems control and data analysis, and of mechanical products with computer-aided design, finite element analysis, and selection of materials.	501 502	512 540 650	511 561 598	HO BSc

1.3 Programme specific elements – Quantitative Biology and Disease Modelling

The B. Sc. in Quantitative Biology and Disease Modelling is a new education started in 2016 where computational and mathematical engineering skills are taught in parallel with biology, pathology, and pharmacology. The goal of the education is for the students to be able to develop quantitative mathematical models of biological and pathological processes. The programme-specific qualifications for the B. Sc. programme in Quantitative Biology and Disease Modelling (QBDM) are listed in *Table 4*.

Table 4. Programme-Qualification matrix, QBDM

		Object complexity→			
-To know		Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
QBDM.K1	Knowledge of biology, physiology and health science: Can <i>classify</i> cellular structures, anatomy and physiology of organ systems and <i>explain</i> form and function with correct use of terminology. Can <i>analyse</i> and <i>interpret</i> histochemical preparations, <i>apply</i> biophysical and bioinformatic principles, and <i>analyse</i> and <i>interpret</i> results of biochemical experiments.	K02 002	K03 K11 022 023	088 089	1SP 4SP BSc
QBDM.K2	Knowledge of pathology, pharmacology and mechanisms of disease: Can <i>define</i> diseases and <i>explain</i> pathogenesis and aetiology. Can <i>account</i> for symptoms and <i>describe</i> diagnosis and treatment. Can <i>explain</i> fundamental pharmacology and bioavailability of drugs.		K03 004	087	1SP BSc
QBDM.K3	Knowledge of quantitative biology: Can use mathematical modelling to <i>analyse</i> and <i>describe</i> physiological processes and disease dynamics within cells, organ systems, and populations. Can use experimental and clinical data to <i>calculate</i> and <i>evaluate</i> selected parameters of pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics.	K02 002 050	K03 004 633 087	088 089	1SP 4SP HO BSc
-To do					
QBDM.D1	Experimental skills: Can <i>design</i> and <i>perform</i> quantitative biochemical, molecular biological and pharmaceutical experiments and <i>collect</i> data with understanding of technical error. Can <i>design</i> and <i>implement</i> computational software for analysis and visualisation of quantitative data.	002	023 087	088 089	1SP HO BSc
QBDM.D2	Mathematical modelling skills: Can <i>perform</i> mathematical modelling of physiological and pathophysiological systems and <i>apply</i> this to <i>analyse</i> and <i>predict</i> the quantitative effect on changes in biological input. Can <i>perform</i> simple PK/PD modelling of drug bioavailability.	002 632	004 050 087 601	088 089	1SP BSc
QBDM.D3	Problem solving – Investigative: Can assist in hypothesis-driven research within cell biology, organ physiology, and disease mechanisms with identification of contributing biological factors model development, mathematical analysis, computer simulations, experiments, and data analysis.	K02 002 050 402	004 023 K11 087	088 089 015	4SP BSc
QBDM.D4	Problem solving – Creative: Can assist in need-driven development of mathematical models for identification of knowledge gaps, new molecular disease targets, and bioprocessing of pharmaceuticals.	002 050	004 K11	088 089 015	4SP BSc

1.4 Programme specific elements – General Engineering

The General Engineering programme is a new international education started in 2016 with approximately half of the students and lecturers having an international background. The education focuses on general engineering competencies and combining these in a cross-disciplinary manner. Further, the programme has great emphasis on Design-Build already from first semester. The students are introduced to the programme's four focus areas—Living Systems, Cyber Systems, Cyber Materials, and Future Energy—and in the following semesters, they will specialize in one of these areas. The four cross-disciplinary specializations makes the programme specific

elements very diverse. However, the qualification elements can still be organized according to the principles suggested in Table 1.

Table 5. Programme-Qualification matrix, General Engineering

		Object complexity→			
-To know		Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
GE.K1	Knowledge of living systems: Can <i>describe</i> basic principles in biochemistry, molecular and cell biology, and ecology. Can <i>account</i> for cell and microbiology and organisms and <i>explain</i> fermentation technology, microbial communities or species interactions.	008 030 701	000 022 023 026 105 201 400	025 034	1SP 4SP BSc
GE.K2	Knowledge of cyber systems: Can <i>examine, select, and apply</i> algorithms and data structures in a general engineering context.	016 135 240	203 157	105 270	1SP 2SP BSc
GE.K3	Knowledge of cyber materials: Can <i>explain</i> the fundamental concepts of materials science and manufacturing technology. Can <i>apply</i> and <i>explain</i> fundamental materials modelling and materials visualization.	018 030 240 680	203 580	502	2SP 3SP BSc
GE.K4	Knowledge of future energy: Can <i>explain</i> the fundamentals of renewable and sustainable energy resources (e.g. wind energy, solar, fuel/electrolyzer cells, batteries). Can <i>explain</i> the fundamentals of energy conversion and storage.	018 030 041 202	260 501 735	201 205	2SP 3SP BSc
-To do					
GE.D1	Experimental skills: Can <i>setup</i> and <i>operate</i> basic laboratory techniques in either molecular biology or process chemistry or ecology. Can <i>setup</i> and <i>operate</i> complementary characterization methods for materials properties and internal structure. Can <i>design, perform, and implement</i> methods for analysis of large amounts and diverse types of data. Can <i>apply</i> the fundamental organization of a computer system in a cyber-physical context. Can <i>design, perform, and implement</i> characterization methods for energy conversion.	016 135 402 680	023 157 203 240 685	027 141 160 205 270	1SP 2SP 3SP 4SP BSc
GE.D2	Mathematical modelling skills: Can <i>implement</i> and <i>apply</i> machine learning algorithms to classify and retrieve patterns in data. Can <i>apply</i> techniques from discrete mathematics in computer science and engineering.	135 601	019	105 141 160	1SP 2SP 3SP 4SP BSc
GE.D3	Problem solving – Investigative: Can <i>assist</i> in hypothesis-driven research within computer-based tools to manage, analyze, and evaluate biological or chemical data. Can <i>analyze</i> and <i>validate</i> computer science models based on discrete mathematics, automata, and semantics. Can <i>assist</i> in hypothesis-driven research within methods and models for engineering materials' performance. Can <i>examine</i> the properties of a component for a range of renewable and sustainable energy technologies. Can <i>analyze</i> simple engineering problems in relation to various renewable and sustainable energy resources and technologies. Can discuss fundamental challenges of implementing sustainable energy solutions into today's society and future approaches. Can compare efficiency of current and future energy technologies.	006 016 135 202 240 402 601 631 680	019 023 157 203 260 501	027 141 160 205 270 526 611	1SP 2SP 3SP 4SP BSc

	... continued	Gen.	Cor.	Spe.	Cap.
GE.D4	<p>Problem solving – Creative:</p> <p>Can demonstrate a fundamental understanding of living systems to <i>solve</i> engineering problems.</p> <p>Can <i>assist</i> in need-driven development of living systems in the context of the environment and its resources and engineered systems.</p> <p>Can <i>assist</i> in need-driven development of appropriate programming paradigm concept to solve a specific engineering problem.</p> <p>Can <i>design</i> and <i>construct</i> small and medium sized programmes.</p> <p>Can <i>assist</i> in need-driven development within prediction of materials properties and performance.</p> <p>Can select materials and <i>engineer</i> them for technical applications.</p> <p>Can <i>assist</i> in need-driven development within materials modelling in relation to material science and engineering.</p> <p>Can <i>select</i> a design of a sustainable energy system to <i>solve</i> a simple engineering problem.</p>	016 022 135 240	023 026 105 157 201 203 260 400 684	000 008 034 141 160 205 270 526	1SP 2SP 3SP 4SP BSc

2 SUMMARY

Inspired by UNESCO's Four pillars of learning [2], the elements of the National Qualification Framework used at DTU were reorganized in a companion paper [1] into four main categories of qualifications: *-to know*, *-to be*, *-to interact*, *-to do*. In the present paper, the revised framework is used to define the educational outcomes in three B. Sc. in Engineering programmes. A set of educational outcomes common to all engineering programmes at DTU is presented, focusing on common knowledge and in particular on competencies characteristic for all engineering programmes (e.g. personal and professional mind-set, self-instruction, communication and teamwork). The common Programme-Qualification Matrix is complemented by programme-specific qualification matrices, where programme content is integrated into the outcome statements. Examples are given here for B. Sc. programmes in Biomedical Engineering, in Quantitative Biology and Disease Modelling, and in General Engineering. The proposed framework aim to facilitate both university-wide uniformity as well as programme-specific focus points. The three qualification matrices presented here, introduce four new elements of educational outcomes (knowledge dimensions, mind-set development, operative skills, and problem solving complexity) none of which previously have been considered in educational programmes at DTU, and which may be implemented while revising the programmes.

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